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TECHEN, A., HELMING, K.

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c/o Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ
Department of Soil System Science
Theodor-Lieser-Str. 4 | 06120 Halle (Saale), Germany
Phone: (+49) 345 558 5226 | E-Mail: info@bonares.de
www.bonares.de

Title	Policy goals as reference points for interdisciplinary soil research
Authors	<p>Techen, Anja-K. – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg</p> <p>Helming, Katharina – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg</p>
Correspondence	anja.techen@zalf.de
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Abstract	<p>Policy goals can be significant reference points for researchers and funders addressing research topics that are relevant for society. Based on a literature and document review we present major current policy goals that are pertaining to the management of agricultural soils, from the global to the national level with a focus on Germany. We highlight the general relevance of these policy goals for interdisciplinary soil research.</p>
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Policy goals as reference points for interdisciplinary soil research

by Anja-K. Techen and Katharina Helming, 2019

1. Introduction

Research has, inter alia, a role to play in providing the evidence base for society to make decisions in direction of policy goals. Goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations (2015b), can be a “*valuable point of reference*” (Bouma and Montanarella, 2016) for researchers choosing research topics that are relevant for society. Soil researchers can provide the knowledge base for policy makers to assess how certain goals can be reached with appropriate soil management measures under current conditions, what kind of changes may have to be made (Bouma and Montanarella, 2016), what unforeseen side-effects pursuing the goals may occur (e.g. Baveye et al., 2018 for the 4 per 1000 initiative) and what trade-offs between the goals may emerge (Helming et al., 2018).

In the following, based on a literature and document review, relevant current policy goals pertaining to the management of agricultural soils are presented with a focus on Germany. This is done to clarify what these aforementioned points of reference for soil researchers and funders are, offering material for reflections on research priorities.

The analysis excludes the crucial but different goal of reducing the loss of agricultural land due to sealing and/or repurposing it e.g. for settlements. “Relevant” refers to the political weight of the goals which is roughly described by characteristics such as the number of countries having adopted a resolution or the existence of monitoring and follow-up procedures and German implementation activities.

The paper is structured as such that first policy goals are presented in a summarized way with their connection to soil functions and soil related ecosystem services (Section 2 with Figure 1). Secondly, soil research implications of the policy goals are outlined (Section 3). For the interested reader, Section 4 depicts the soil related policy goals in more detail, quasi being an annex to Section 2. It ends on an outlook on upcoming goal-settings in the European Union (Section 4.3), being crucial for future developments in member states’ goal-settings and implementation of goals.

2. Policy goals and their connection to soil functions and soil related ecosystems services

The connection between policy goals and agricultural soils can be made via the five soil functions: (i) production of biomass, (ii) storing and filtering of water, (iii) storing and recycling of nutrients, (iv) habitat for organisms, and (v) carbon storage (Vogel et al., 2018) and the emanating ecosystem services (see Figure 1). The production function of the soil and the resulting ecosystem services of provision of food, energy and material are, for example, connected to bioeconomy goals and the “zero hunger” goal of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 2). The carbon storage function and climate mitigation service are connected to the “climate action” goal (SDG 13) and the climate policy with the Paris Agreement and the 4 per 1000 goal. The habitat function and biodiversity services are connected to the “life on land” goal (SDG 15) and the biodiversity policy with the Aichi Targets. Some goals, such as the SDGs, and those implied by the World Soil Charter and the EU Grand Societal Challenges, are connected to a broad range of soil functions and respective ecosystem services. Since the focus is here on agricultural soils, the soil functions material supply, human habitat and cultural

heritage are only marginally mentioned. The goals are described below in Section 4, including the references to the relevant documents.

3. Soil research implications of the policy goals

Those policy goals, many of them expressed unanimously on the global level as well as on the EU and national levels, have soil under agricultural production as a fundamental component directly or indirectly in the context of the bioeconomy, climate mitigation and adaptation, sustainable development, and biodiversity. However, the goals do not all go into the same direction and trade-offs between goals occur.

Figure 1: Soil functions and ecosystem services (adopted from Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016) and policy goals for which they are relevant (symbols taken from sources cited in the text).

The German bioeconomy strategy represents the core conflict, underlying many policies (e.g. agricultural policy, SDGs): On the one hand, a goal is that the production of food and biomass for industrial and energetic purposes is to be increased, which implies an intensification of production due to limited availability of land. On the other hand, pressures on soils are to be reduced to preserve soil functions permanently, thus allowing other ecosystem services, such as “nutrition, energy”, “climate mitigation, nutrient capacity”, “regulating water and nutrients” and “biodiversity”, to be realized. This shows that soil research must have an important role in implementing those goals, particularly in the following steps:

- To realize the goals, soil management measures have to be developed, which minimize the trade-offs between the production goals and the conservation goals.

- Once effective soil management measures are available, wanted and unwanted impacts have to be assessed before broad implementation, also specifying trade-offs between goal achievements.
- During and after the implementation, monitoring and evaluation procedures have to be conducted at different spatial levels.

Therefore, policy goals imply research needs in the areas of developing agricultural production systems under conscious usage of soil processes, soil process models, indicators and methods for ex-ante and ex-post assessments as well as for spatial aggregation and disaggregation (up- and downscaling).

4. The policy goals in detail

In the following, first, the policy goals are presented that are set in policy strategies focusing explicitly on soils (4.1). Thereafter, policy goals are presented, which address soils but are set in other policy fields, namely sustainable development, climate change, biodiversity and bioeconomy (4.2). While sections 4.1 and 4.2 focus on global and national goals, skipping the intermediary European level, Section 4.3 summarizes the European level. An outlook on the current developments in the EU concludes Section 4 and the paper.

4.1 Soil focused policy goals in explicit soil strategies

Even though goals for soil use have not been established in an explicit way in international regimes on the same high levels as sustainability (Section 4.2.1), climate (4.2.2) and biodiversity goals (4.2.3), soil issues have been addressed in the United Nations framework. While in 1981 the first **World Soil Charter** was created and endorsed by all FAO members (now 194 member nations), the revised one was endorsed in 2015. Even though the Charter gives action guidelines rather than goals, the Charter clearly states that *“the overarching goal for all parties is to ensure that soils are managed sustainably and that degraded soils are rehabilitated or restored.”* (FAO, 2015). The World Soil Charter is embedded in the framework of the Global Soil Partnership (GSP) and its associated Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soils (ITPS) which were established in 2011 and 2013 respectively (FAO, 2016) which all have not found the desirable attention and necessary activity yet (Montanarella, 2015).

While the realization of these international goals must be pursued by the member states, agricultural soil goals are hardly addressed explicitly at the German national level. The **Federal Soil Protection Act** expresses a goal by giving the Act the comprehensive purpose of preserving and restoring soil functions (BBodSchG § 1). At the same time, concrete rules and actions that can further the achievement of these goals are scattered in other goal fields, such as in the Fertilization Ordinance and the “protein crops strategy” (BMEL and BLE, 2016).

4.2 Soil related goals in other policy strategies

4.2.1 Soil related goals in the Sustainable Development Goals

The 2030 Agenda with the 17 **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** (United Nations, 2015b), is a major political step in addressing global problems, including agricultural soil use. The UN-General Assembly, with 193 members, adopted it in September of 2015. Other than the Millennium Development Goals, the SDGs are more comprehensive in their thematic spectrum and in addressing sustainable development. Furthermore, the adopted resolution involves specifications on how to implement the SDGs and how to follow-up and review the progress, however without specific legally binding obligations for member states.

The SDGs contain several goals and, as subcategory of these, targets which pertain to a sustainable, efficient and effective soil management. Soil is targeted both explicitly and implicitly, with soil being an important part of the addressed systems. The central “soil” goal is SDG 15 – target 3 (SDG 15.3), pertaining to all the soil functions that are needed and influenced by agriculture: achieving a land degradation neutral world by 2030 and restoring degraded land and soil. Other goals address soil explicitly (2.4, 3.9, 12.4) or they address functions of soil for food, biomass and energy production (2.3, 7.2), climate mitigation (13.2), water and substance regulation (2.4, 3.9, 13.1) and soil as habitat for biodiversity (15.5), all relevant for agricultural soil management or soil as a whole (12.2, 12.4, 15.3, 8.4). Furthermore, natural heritage (11.4) and the physical and cultural environment for mankind (11.7) are addressed and from a broader perspective soil can be attributed to these and even more goals, such as the reduction of poverty (goal 1) and clean waters (6.6, 14.1) (e.g. Weigelt et al., 2015).

The goals and targets have to be operationalized with indicators for monitoring progress. In the global indicator framework for the SDGs (General Assembly, 2017) soil is implicitly mentioned as the central part of land in the indicator “Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area” for Goal 15 – target 3.

Germany has decided to implement its national contribution to the SDGs within the **German sustainability strategy** (“Nachhaltigkeitsstrategie”) (Deutsche Bundesregierung, 2017) which was revised in 2018, inter alia to adjust it to the SDGs (Deutsche Bundesregierung, 2018). In this strategy, the sustainable management of agricultural soils in Germany is mainly represented by the indicators “nitrogen surplus” and “share of organic agriculture”, for SDG 2 (“zero hunger”), and their target values (see Section 4.3) while indirectly, soils are playing a role, just as in the UN SDGs, in several national targets. However, specifically for SDG 15.3 (“By 2030, [...], achieve a land degradation-neutral world”) there is no agricultural indicator but only the indicator “deforestation”. There is no indicator and no target for soil quality. But at least the aim is to develop an indicator for “soil protection” by 2020 (ibid.).

For the global level, Germany has decided to orient its development policy on the SDGs until 2030 (BMZ, 2015) and, for example, has signed a special initiative by nine countries, committing themselves to, and calling for, supporting the implementation of the SDGs (Government Offices of Sweden, 2015).

4.2.2 Soil related goals in the field of climate change mitigation and adaptation

The 21st Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC (UNFCCC, 1992) (COP21) led to the **Paris Agreement** (United Nations, 2015a) which is widely seen as ground-breaking, especially because 195 UNFCCC members have agreed on legally binding targets of climate mitigation (keeping temperature rise below 2°C and try to limit it under 1.5°C above pre-industrial level), adaptation efforts and providing the financial resources for implementation (§2 (1) FCCC/CP/2015/L.9/Rev.1). To date 185 Parties have ratified the agreement (UNFCCC Secretariat, 2019). The countries have to produce “nationally determined contributions” (NDCs) every five years with increasing efforts, respectively a “progression over time” (§3 ff. FCCC/CP/2015/L.9/Rev.1). Compliance will be controlled by a committee. Sanctions to enforce compliance cannot be imposed, though.

Although not mentioning soil in the Paris Agreement it is obvious that soil and agriculture play a key role in mitigation of, and adaptation to, climate change. This is reflected in 161 intended nationally determined contributions (INDCs) by 189 Parties, covering 99 % of GHG emissions of all Parties to the Convention, that were handed in by April 2016 (UNFCCC Secretariat, 2016)¹: 74% and 73% of the INDCs covered the sectors “Agriculture” and “LULUCF” (land use, land-use change and forestry). Additionally, “Agriculture” is one of the priority areas for adaptation (ibid.).

To realize its own commitments to reduce GHG emissions by 40 % below the 1990 level by 2020 and 80-95 % by 2050, the German government has created a “**National Climate Action Plan for 2050**” (Deutsche Bundesregierung, 2016). “Agriculture” and “Land use and forestry” are two of six fields of action. For “Agriculture” the core aims are to reduce nitrogen emissions (sectoral surplus of 70 kg/ha by 2032 and still decreasing) and to increase the share of organic agriculture from 6.3 in 2014 to 20 %, both with relevance for agricultural soil management. No turning over of grassland on moor soils is one minor aim in the section “Land use and forestry”. Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils is not in the focus of the National Climate Action Plan but Germany is also member of the “**4 per 1000**” initiative. As there is theoretically a big potential to store more carbon in soils, and this could at the same time support adaptation to climate change and fertility of soils, thus also to food security, the French government had launched the “4 per 1000” initiative in 2015 which is supported by many other states, research facilities, NGOs and other organizations (Ministère de l'Agriculture, 2015/2016). They propose as the initiative’s first stage, to involve all relevant stakeholders in an action programme and a research programme (Ministry of agriculture, 2016). However, the basic ideas of the 4 per 1000 initiative have been heavily challenged by some leading soil researchers (Baveye et al., 2018) and the last COP to the UNFCCC in November 2017 had not taken the topic up (Rumpel et al., 2018).

4.2.3 Soil related goals in the field of biodiversity

While the political recognition of biodiversity’s relevance has recently been strengthened by the adoption of the formerly mentioned SDGs, the world had already set up biodiversity goals in the framework of the Convention on Biodiversity (CBD, 196 member countries): The **Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020** with the **20 Aichi Biodiversity Targets** (COP to the CBD, 2010a) were adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the CBD (COP to the CBD) in 2010, complemented by a decision

¹ By July 2019 184 had submitted their actual nationally determined contributions (NDCs) (UNFCCC Secretariat, 2018) but the following analysis is based on the INDCs from 2016 because no more current analysis was available.

for the implementation of the strategy and the targets (COP to the CBD, 2010b). Similarly like the 2030 Agenda, the Aichi Biodiversity Targets comprise no specific legally binding obligations (Harrop, 2011). The implementation of the strategy involves the establishment of national targets and their incorporation into the National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs), which are required according to the CBD (Article. 6). While the mid-term review showed the need for additional efforts to achieve the targets (Tittensor et al., 2014), the launch of a three year study to measure the progress towards the targets in the last years of the strategies' implementation (IPBES, 2016) may be an indicator of renewed attention towards these policy goals.

The 20 Aichi targets are organized in five goals. The word "soil" does not occur but soil biodiversity is an essential part of the addressed targets which include overarching and procedural ones such as awareness of people of the biodiversity values (target 1) and using participatory policy instruments (target 17). Most concretely two targets concern agricultural soil as habitat: target 7 ("*By 2020, areas under agriculture, [...] are managed sustainably, ensuring conservation of biodiversity.*") and 8 ("*By 2020, pollution, including from excess nutrients, has been brought to levels that are not detrimental to ecosystem function and biodiversity*").

Germany had submitted its **National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plan in 2007** (BMUB, 2007) and not changed since. Soil as a habitat is explicitly part of the German targets, mostly so in target B 2.5 "soil use" of which the core is that natural soil functions will be maintained in the long-term so that "*Germany possesses a natural diversity of soils which have evolved over the course of history, are typical of the region, and fulfil a range of functions for man and nature. They offer favourable living conditions for the location-typical species and biotic communities which live in, on and from the soils.*" (ibid.). Additionally, target B 3.1 specifically concerns biodiversity in agricultural soils by aiming for, among others, reduced nutrient loads to agricultural soils. The German government initiated several communication processes for a participatory implementation of the strategy and started a funding program for projects (BfN, n.d.). Since in 2014 a progress report showed that the efforts made were not sufficient to achieve the targets, the government started an additional programme, the "Naturschutz-Offensive 2020" (BMUB, 2015), thereby giving renewed policy emphasize to the biodiversity goals. These biodiversity goals call for closing research gaps pertaining to soil biodiversity including research on indicators for monitoring to assess progress and effectivity of soil management measures.

4.2.4 Soil related goals in the field of bioeconomy

Bioeconomy strategies exist in Germany as well as on the level of the EU and globally in different countries such as the USA, Russia and India explicitly or partially by promoting single bioeconomical sectors (Albrecht und Ettlting, 2014). "*Bioeconomy is characterised by economic activities deriving from scientific and research activities that are linked to different forms of biotechnology. It turns life science knowledge, meaning the scientific study of living organisms, into sustainable, eco-efficient and competitive products.*" (Albrecht and Ettlting, 2014). It also includes the goal to replace fossil-based raw materials by renewable raw materials (ibid.). Thus, on the one hand, the pressure on agricultural soils increases because more biological raw materials, such as different kinds of crops, have to be produced. On the other hand, the bioeconomy strategies present soil research needs in the context of, for example, cultivating newly bred crops and of developing new or adapted production systems.

The societal challenges stemming from the bioeconomy have been recognized in the **German bioeconomy strategy** that sets the goals of creating a sustainable bioeconomy, protecting the environment, including soil fertility and soil functions, biodiversity and climate and considering social issues (BMEL, 2014). After all, the crucial role of soil and the need for soil research to ensure a sustainable bioeconomy, has been recognized by the German government, initiating the BonaRes funding programme, offering funding for interdisciplinary research projects and a BonaRes Centre for nine years. Goals defined by this funding programme are the optimization of soil functions, the efficient management of water and nutrient utilization, and the optimization of farming strategies and soil use management (BMBF, 2013). Along with this, *“one major focus is to be on understanding the significance of biotic soil factors”* (ibid.).

4.3 Soil goals in the EU and upcoming goal-setting decisions

The previously mentioned goals were shown mostly on a global level and specified for Germany. However, all of these goals are also represented on the EU level. To acknowledge this, the overarching **Grand Societal Challenges** shall be named. Those were established in the context of the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020, thus being a foundation for formulating research needs and allocating funds to research. Almost 38% of the Horizon 2020 budget of 78.6 billion € have been allocated to research tackling those Grand Societal Challenges (Wissenschaftsrat, 2015). Two of those seven challenges involve soil issues, namely *“food security, sustainable agriculture, [...] and bioeconomy”*, and *“climate action, environment, resource efficiency [...]”*.

Additionally, soil related goals have been mentioned in some European Commission documents, predominantly in the **Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe** (Paleari, 2017). Pertaining to agricultural soils, central in this roadmap (European Commission, 2011) is the goal to reduce soil erosion and increase organic matter by 2020. Even though the establishment of a Soil Framework Directive failed, soil protection was at least supported to some degree in the frame of the Soil Thematic Strategy (Panagos and Montanarella, 2018). Furthermore, the **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** contains soil goals (European Parliament and Council, 2013). But in practice, they, along with other environmental and societal goals, stand in contrast to still predominating production goals (Recanati et al., 2019). As a consequence, assessments of the Greening of the CAP show rather limited impacts on environmental issues (Cortignani and Dono, 2019, Pe'er et al., 2016). Gocht et al. (2017) even estimate that soil erosion might slightly be increasing under the CAP Greening. It remains to be seen whether this will change under the CAP 2021-2027. At least verbally the proposals from the European Commission show a clear trend towards a greater orientation on environmental and sustainability goals, among them the goal of *“foster[ing] sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air”* (European Commission, 2018b). Currently this still stands in contrast to production oriented goals in the proposals and the chances of serious pursuit of sustainability goals in the CAP 2021-2027 are small (Pe'er et al., 2019). But if those goals should after all be taken serious, the CAP could play a very important role for soil improving agricultural management and supporting soil functions. This development could be reinforced and further supported by **Horizon Europe**, which is the next European Framework Program for Research and Innovation 2021-2027 with a proposed budget of 100 billion € (European Commission, 2019). Therein, ‘soil health and food’ is planned to be one of five missions the program is dedicated to. Figure 2 below may then replace Figure 1 and thereby becomes a hopeful closure of this overview.

Figure 2: Soil functions and ecosystem services (adopted from Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016) and policy goals for which they are relevant with an outlook on upcoming decisions in EU goal setting (symbols taken from sources cited in the text plus for the CAP: European Commission, 2018a and for Horizon Europe: European Commission 2018c).

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